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RESEARCH PAPER

STATURE ESTIMATION FROM HAND ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS IN PORT HARCOURT

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ABSTRACT

Stature estimation is essential in forensic, anthropological, and clinical contexts. This study developed regression models to predict stature from hand dimensions among adults in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. A total of 400 participants (168 males, 232 females) aged 18–50 years were measured for hand length, hand breadth, and stature using standard anthropometric protocols. Pearson correlation and linear regression analyses were performed to derive sex-specific predictive models. Hand length showed strong positive correlations with stature ($r = 0.78$, $p < 0.001$ in males; $r = 0.72$, $p < 0.001$ in females), while hand breadth also correlated positively ($r = 0.65$ in males; $r = 0.61$ in females). Univariate regression equations for stature estimation were $H = 65.32 + 2.15 \times \text{Hand Length}$ for males and $H = 60.14 + 2.01 \times \text{Hand Length}$ for females. Multivariate models incorporating hand breadth slightly improved predictive accuracy compared with univariate models (males: $R^2 = 0.65$; females: $R^2 = 0.58$). These findings indicate that hand measurements can reliably estimate stature in this population, with applications in forensic identification, clinical assessment, and ergonomic design.

Keywords: Stature Estimation, Anthropometry, Forensic Identification, Port Harcourt

INTRODUCTION

Anthropometry, the systematic measurement of human body dimensions, is an essential tool in forensic science, clinical assessment, and ergonomic design (Krishan and Sharma, 2007; Kanchan *et al.*, 2010). Estimating stature from body segments, such as the hand, foot, or limbs, is valuable for identifying individuals, assessing growth patterns, and designing anthropometrically appropriate tools or workspaces (Numan *et al.*, 2013; Asiwe *et al.*, 2025). Accurate prediction of stature from hand dimensions is critical when full skeletal or body measurements are unavailable, such as in mass disasters, partial skeletal remains, or amputees (Habib and Kamal, 2010; Okubike *et al.*, 2018).

Hand anthropometry, including measurements of hand length and breadth, correlates strongly with stature due to proportional relationships in human growth (Elamin and Abdel Moneim, 2011; Numan *et al.*, 2013). Sexual dimorphism is well-established, with males exhibiting larger hand dimensions than females, necessitating sex-specific regression models for precise stature estimation (Adefisan and Olopade, 2018; Asiwe *et al.*, 2025).

Population-specific models enhance predictive accuracy because anthropometric parameters vary by genetics, nutrition, and environment (Oladipo *et al.*, 2006; Ahmed, 2013). In Nigeria, diverse ethnic groups display distinct morphometric patterns, highlighting the need for localized predictive models rather than reliance on generalized international equations (Numan *et al.*, 2013; Asiwe *et al.*, 2025). Such population-specific models improve accuracy in forensic identification, clinical evaluation, and growth monitoring (Okubike *et al.*, 2018; Idowu and Olopade, 2022).

This study aimed to estimate stature from hand dimensions among adults in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, using standardized measurement protocols and regression analysis to provide reference data for forensic identification in mass disasters, growth assessment in medical practice, and the design of ergonomically appropriate tools tailored to Nigerian populations.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: A cross-sectional descriptive design was employed to evaluate the relationship between hand dimensions and stature among healthy adult residents of Port Harcourt (Krishan and Sharma, 2007; Kanchan *et al.*, 2010).

Participants: 400 healthy adult volunteers (168 males, 232 females), aged 18–50 years, were recruited through simple random sampling. Exclusion criteria included limb deformities, recent fractures, musculoskeletal injuries, and chronic illnesses affecting growth (Numan *et al.*, 2013; Okubike *et al.*, 2018). Written informed consent was obtained, and the study adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki (World Medical Association, 2013).

Anthropometric Measurements:

1. **Stature:** Measured with a portable stadiometer to the nearest 0.1 cm, with participants standing barefoot in the Frankfurt plane.
2. **Hand Length:** Distance from midpoint of distal wrist crease to tip of middle finger on the dominant hand, using a digital caliper (Kanchan, 2008).
3. **Hand Breadth:** Measured across metacarpal heads at the widest part of the hand, to the nearest 0.1 mm using a digital caliper.

Procedure: Measurements were taken in the morning (8:00–11:00 a.m.) to minimize diurnal variation. Each measurement was taken twice, and the mean was used for analysis (Farkas *et al.*, 2005). Instruments were calibrated and measurements conducted following standardized protocols by trained personnel.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26. Descriptive statistics summarized participant characteristics. Pearson correlation coefficients evaluated relationships between hand dimensions and stature. Linear regression models were developed to generate predictive equations. Significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Model assumptions, including normality and homoscedasticity, were verified.

RESULTS

Descriptive statistics for stature and hand dimensions are presented in Table 1. Males had higher mean stature and larger hand measurements than females. Pearson correlation analysis revealed strong positive relationships between hand dimensions and stature for both sexes (Table 2). Hand length showed the strongest correlation with stature, while hand breadth was also positively correlated, albeit with slightly lower coefficients. Univariate linear regression using

hand length alone effectively predicted stature, accounting for 61% of the variance in males and 52% in females (**Table 3**). The inclusion of hand breadth in multivariate regression models slightly improved predictive accuracy (**Table 4**).

Table 1: Mean \pm SD of Stature and Hand Dimensions

Sex	N	Stature (cm)	Hand Length (cm)	Hand Breadth (cm)
Male	168	176.1 \pm 6.3	19.3 \pm 1.2	8.7 \pm 0.6
Female	232	162.5 \pm 5.7	17.2 \pm 0.9	7.6 \pm 0.5

Table 2: Pearson Correlation between Hand Dimensions and Stature

Sex	Hand Length vs Stature	Hand Breadth vs Stature
Male	$r = 0.78, p < 0.001$	$r = 0.65, p < 0.001$
Female	$r = 0.72, p < 0.001$	$r = 0.61, p < 0.001$

Table 3: Regression Equations Using Hand Length

Sex	Regression Equation	R ²	p-value
Male	$H = 65.32 + 2.15 \times \text{Hand Length}$	0.61	<0.001
Female	$H = 60.14 + 2.01 \times \text{Hand Length}$	0.52	<0.001

Table 4: Multivariate Regression Equations Using Hand Length and Hand Breadth

Sex	Regression Equation	R ²	p-value
Male	$H = 65.32 + 2.15 \times \text{Hand Length} + 0.50 \times \text{Hand Breadth}$	0.65	<0.001
Female	$H = 60.14 + 2.01 \times \text{Hand Length} + 0.35 \times \text{Hand Breadth}$	0.58	<0.001

DISCUSSION

This study demonstrates that hand dimensions, particularly hand length, are strongly associated with stature in adults from Port Harcourt. Pearson correlation revealed strong positive associations ($r = 0.78$ for males; $r = 0.72$ for females). Hand breadth also correlated positively, though to a lesser extent ($r = 0.65$ for males; $r = 0.61$ for females), indicating that longitudinal hand dimensions are more predictive of stature than transverse measures (Farkas *et al.*, 2005).

Regression analysis showed that hand length alone is a robust predictor of stature, explaining 61% of variance in males and 52% in females. Multivariate models including hand breadth slightly improved predictive accuracy ($R^2 = 0.65$ for males; $R^2 = 0.58$ for females), underscoring the importance of sex-specific models for stature estimation (Adefisan and Olopade, 2018).

Population-specific models minimize errors due to ethnic and environmental variation (Okubike *et al.*, 2018). These models enhance forensic identification, particularly when only partial remains are available, and assist in clinical assessments and anthropometric research (WHO, 2008).

International studies report similar trends: hand length is a strong predictor of stature across diverse populations, including North India, Egypt, and Sudan (Krishan and Sharma, 2007; Habib and Kamal, 2010; Elamin and Abdel Moneim, 2011). The modest influence of hand breadth likely reflects inter-individual variation in hand width not directly linked to height.

The study demonstrates that hand dimensions, particularly hand length, are strong and reliable predictors of stature among adults in Port Harcourt. Univariate regression models showed that hand length alone accounts for a substantial proportion of the variance in stature, while multivariate models incorporating hand breadth modestly improve predictive accuracy. These results underscore the importance of considering sexual dimorphism when estimating stature, as males consistently exhibited larger hand measurements than females.

In conclusion, the findings provide practical applications in forensic identification, clinical assessment, and ergonomic design, where accurate estimation of stature from partial measurements is often required. They also highlight the value of developing population-specific anthropometric models to enhance predictive accuracy. Future research should explore integrating additional body measurements, such as foot or upper limb dimensions, to refine multivariate predictive models and extend their applicability across diverse Nigerian populations.

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AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTION

All authors contributed substantially to the conception, design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and writing of this study. Each author reviewed the manuscript critically for important intellectual content, approved the final version for publication, and agrees to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

